

OPTIMIZATION OF ANESTHOLOGICAL CARE IN SCHEDULED GYNECOLOGICAL OPERATIONS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7007273>

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Abstract: *This article discusses the optimization of anesthesiological support in planned gynecological operations, what is anesthesiology, the transition processes of gynecological surgery and how to use anesthesiological support.*

Key words: *Anesthesiology, clinic, surgery, operation, pathology, diet.*

Абстракт: *В данной статье рассматривается оптимизация анестезиологического обеспечения при плановых гинекологических операциях, что такое анестезиология, переходные процессы гинекологической хирургии и как использовать анестезиологическое обеспечение.*

Ключевые слова: *анестезиология, клиника, хирургия, операция, патология, диета.*

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada rejali ginekologik operatsiyalarda anesteziologik yordamni optimallashtirish anesteziologiya nima ekanligi, ginekologik operatsiya o'tish jarayonlari va anesteziologik yordamdan qanday foydalanish haqida so'z yuritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Anesteziologiya, klinik, [jarrohlik](#), operatsiya, patologiya, ratsion.*

Anesthesiology is studying the issues of anesthesia in the clinical nature, the surgery, management of its important vital functions during surgery. Anesthesiology has formed a few decades before as an independent science. Anesthesiology service in Uzbekistan is fluffed; There are special anesthesiology departments in major hospitals. The departments of anesthesiology are prepared and research work is carried out.

Among most diseases of the women's reproduction system are often treated through surgical intervention. In this case, all gynecological operations can be divided into planned and emergency.

1. Emergency equipment is done immediately after the pathology that requires emergency intervention. For example, without pregnancy outside pregnancy, the practice of pregnancy with pregnancy should be done as

soon as possible. The reason for this can cause internal bleeding or peritonitis that can lead to death.

2. When planned, initial training of gynecological patients (prePreparation) is carried out. Thus, the woman gives many tests before gynecological surgery: blood, urine, ankg, ultrasound. Due to the use of total anesthesia for gynecological operations, doctors predetermine the woman's tolerantism compared to certain medicines and the presence of anamnesis operations.

There are 2 types of gynecological operations:

1. Kaviter;
2. Small.

The main difference is that when it is first done, the abdominal wall of the woman is cut and the other passes through via Via.

Causel gynecological transactions are before the long runs of the woman in the hospital and prepared for surgery.

Mandatory condition is a mandatory condition - this is to follow the diet. Thus, when preparing for gynecological surgery, solid food is completely excluded from the ration of the woman. 12 hours before surgery, the woman is prescribed toxic obstruction. If a woman is very worried about surgery, the sedaniv is prescribed. Like any operation, a gynecological examination is conducted in the intestinal cavity and the urine.

Anestnesiological care in scheduled gynecological operations, first of all, to facilitate the patient before surgery, to prevent incoming neutroval reactions, and the side effects of hyperalivation and other processes is dependent on.

The operation is carried out under general anesthesia to prevent pain in women. In the postgrap period of the anesthesia, only when the cervix is opened and allowed the organ expanded.

Once anesthesia is inserted, a friendly place is disinfected, servications will be opened, then operation will be opened.

There are several ways to do this:

1. Manually cleaning. This is done using a special syringe. This method consists of sucks of uterus under the influence of the impaired embryo violation. The process is managed by the doctor.

2. Clean the machine. This involves the use of a special pump to get a fetal.

The process does not exceed four per hour. In addition, we recommend reading information about the term of vacuum abortia and its behavior.

This type of surgical intervention is the uterus of the operating body, and more precisely, includes all the operations with its height.

Thus, the operation belonging to this type is often the Servix plastic often in its vaginal section. It is done simultaneously with the hypertrophy of the Service Channel and chronic lateral rupture of services.

In recent decades, the role of anesthesiologists is expanding and not only to send painkismate devices during surgery, but also to identify high-risk patients and optimize their physical fitness. Periodative medicine called a situation to understand the situation, to improve security, as well as peripheral to encourage and strengthen later recovery.

An effective practice of anestheticology requires several practical knowledge, some of them:

-Fermitology includes inhalation anesthetics, local anesthetics and vasopressors (e.ganzetron, glyliciratulation).

-Monisters: electrocardiography, electromocidiography, electricity, electromy and encopulation monitoring, nervous-muscles and cortic stimulation map and neuromorphology.

-Mechanical ventilation.

-Annatomical knowledge Nervous system for the nerve blocks of the nervous blocks of and others.

Information about the influence of other areas of medicine (e.g., cardiology, pulmonology, obstetricity), which is affected by some age groups (newborns, pediatrics, Geriatrics).

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